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Annotation. The century of digital technology has brought information presentation to a new, higher level of quality. Thanks to computers and presentation software, anyone can compile a report covering any topic in an understandable format. Only the right knowledge and the right software are needed for a successful presentation.

Key words: technology, method, programs, encourage, improvement.

The following article deals with the types of software presentations, which are one of the most effective method of teaching. The main focus of this approach is the process rather than the product. Learners learn language by using four types of language skills and purposefully while engaged in the activities and tasks. Activities and tasks can be either: those that learners might need to achieve in real life; those that have a pedagogical purpose specific to the classroom.

Technology is evolving rapidly in the past two decades. Many are familiar with technology and gradually becoming digital natives. In this technological era, the application of technology has eased our ways in various fields of work particularly in the education field. Technology has also proven its effectiveness in language teaching which includes as a source of motivation and provides room for authentic learning.

Our country draws a special attention to strengthening learning and teaching foreign languages of our youth targeting at forming conditions and chance for fostering international collaboration and communication, widely and effectively using the advance achievements of the world civilization and the information sources as well as providing their integration into the world mutual society.

Nowadays, in Uzbekistan the results of nation - wide reforms in the sphere of education basing on the laws as “On Education” and “National Program of Personnel Training” create an opportunity for our youth gaining qualitative education in the thousands of new educational institutions. Created conditions in the field of education serve for bringing up well – educated, modern, intelligently thoughtful, intellectually and harmoniously developed generation, who get complete professional preparation.

On December 10, 2012 the implementation of the Presidential Decree № 1875 on “The measures of strengthening the system of learning foreign languages” created the basis for reforming on teaching foreign languages According to the decree, starting from 2013/2014 school year foreign languages, mainly English gradually throughout the country will be taught from the first year of schooling in the form of the lessons games and speaking games continuing to learning the alphabet reading, spelling, in the second year(grade).¹

As a result the following concluding remarks and recommendations can be recorded:

¹ the Presidential Decree № 1875 on “The measures of strengthening the system of learning foreign languages”

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- Theory and practice in the foreign language learning can be matched together by the usage of modern technology.
- Modern technical ways should be followed for effective learning and teaching of the second language.
- English language teachers should encourage their students to use technology in developing the language skills.

The purpose of the work is to illustrate the importance and necessity of using technology in teaching, based on reflections of English language teaching experience. The work provides opportunities to integrate current knowledge and beliefs of language teaching and learning with new approaches and methods gained during the course. In this paper, we will try to explore some effective ways of teaching reading and writing in ESL classroom, by expressing new ways of implementing technology tools as well as pointing out some challenges and solutions to them.

Technology is no longer foreign to the earth's citizens. Technology has played its role in multiple fields of work, particularly in education. During the last two decades, the implementation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in language education has become a real topic of interest. The use of technology has become significant in the teaching and learning process in and out of class. Technology opens a window of improvement in language learning. Not only that, technology allows teachers to enhance classroom activities and language learning process. This shows that there is a brand-new era which assigns challenging responsibilities for modern teachers. The traditional teaching method has been changed drastically with extraordinary access to technology. The implementation of technology has provided options for a more interesting and productive teaching and learning sessions predominantly in language learning.

According to Shyamlee and Phil², technology has provided significant drivers for both social and linguistic change. With English as an international language and its development around the world, English is used as a second language in a country such as India and Malaysia. To some people, English acts as their first language. English has become the language for instruction and curriculum in many countries. As the number of English learners increases, new teaching methods have been implemented to test the effectiveness of the teaching process. Language is one of the most substantial elements in communication. Students utilize different parts of English language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing for their proficiency and communication. Research has found multiple shreds of evidences of the use of information and communication technology (ICT) on students. Rosicka and Mayerova stated that the purpose of the new era of education is to make the current and upcoming generation active participants in society with the implementation of technology. Harwati stated that the current generation is being called digital natives as they have a high level of computer literacy. It would be utterly unimaginable if the new era of education does not implement technology as a medium of communication and exchanging ideas. Using computers as learning tools can promote efficient learning when learners are engaged in knowledge construction, collaboration, and reflection.

The use of ICT in the education field has been increasing. Educational technologies promised to change the way teachers teach and students learn forever The white canvas of language teaching and

² Shyamlee, S. D., & Phil, M. (2012). Use of Technology in English Language Teaching and Learning: An Analysis. In International Conference on Language, Medias and Culture (Vol. 33, pp. 150-156).

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learning has experienced major creativity and changes over the decade with the emerging of a new era of education and technology. Technology has transformed the field of education, lower and higher education, which has a great impact on the field of English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching. As time changed, teachings changed too.

The technology implementation is defined as “the process of determining which electronic tools and which methods from implementing them are the most appropriate responses to give classroom situations and problems”.³ Computer-assisted language learning (CALL) has become normalized in the educational process. The key to a successful use of technology in teaching and learning session not only lies in hardware or software but also in our human ability as teachers have to plan, design and implement effective educational activities. Educational multimedia is currently being used commonly in teaching and learning of English language. Another commonly used element in the digital era as part of technology would be social media. Social media augments the learning experience by allowing the learners and teachers to connect and interact in a more innovative and interesting way. Social media such as Facebook, Blog, Instagram, e-mail and Twitter provide a platform where users can interact and exchange ideas as well as to find answers through collaboration and discussion.

With the help of technology, students’ view on learning has shifted. New and more advanced technologies are not only transforming the way the students’ view learning but also transforming the way “educators think about education and literacy”. These tools are also continuing to grow and transform literacy instruction” and they also helping students to “internalize lifelong skills needed for success in this global society. Technology will not substitute great teachers but technology in the hands of great teachers can be transformational.

Educational technologies are becoming increasingly important and promise to change the way students learn and teachers teach. However, technology has been around in language teaching for decades. For example, the blackboard, as a form of technology, has been used for centuries. Tape recorders, language labs and videos have been in use since the 1960s and 1970s, and are still used in classrooms around the world (Dudeny and Hockly, 2008). The use of technology in the classroom is becoming increasingly important for the presentation of authentic materials and hopefully it will become a normal part of ELT practice in the coming years. Yet teacher training programs often ignore training in the use of ICT, and teachers are often far less skilled than their own students when it comes to using current technology.

It is a good time to consider the power of current technological advances. Increasingly, communication and information technologies have become part of our everyday lives. The use of computers is increasing day by day, because they are used in many fields to make our lives easier. Computers can present crucial information and offer effective tutorial instruction. Computers also connect us with other people, store vast amounts of data, and provide us with access and entertainment. In the technology literature, learning theories have offered different views regarding the use of computer technology. For instance, behaviorism proposed that learning from technologies means using computers for drill and practice, because learning, according to this view, is a matter of imitation and practice. Thus, the behavioral view strongly advocated that the role of adults in learning is important, as they provide a model by which children learn through imitation; the adults also

³ Roy, A. (2019). Technology in Teaching and Learning. *International Journal of Innovation Education and Research*, 7, 414-422. <https://doi.org/10.31686/ijer.Vol7.Iss4.1433>

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encourage children to continue using computer technology by providing them with positive reinforcement. In contrast to behaviorism, the socioconstructivist theory suggests that if the learner learns with computer technology, the role of the computer is to foster, scaffold, and enhance learning in meaningful ways. When learning with technology, a learner should be given many opportunities to create, test, and reverse their hypotheses. Therefore, teachers have a responsibility to provide learners with these experiences to promote their development.

Technology in general is becoming increasingly important in our personal and professional lives. Dictionaries and scholars have offered a variety of definitions. The Merriam-Webster dictionary, for example, defines technology as "the practical application of knowledge especially in a particular area". Technology is also considered as a body of knowledge used to create tools and develop skills, and as the combination of scientific method and material to meet an objective or solve a problem. Most of these definitions broadly define technology as the knowledge, skills, methods, and techniques used to accomplish specific practical tasks. Educational technologies, in this sense, promise to change forever the way students learn and teachers teach. However, technology in language teaching is not new. It has been around in language teaching for decades. For example, the blackboard, as a form of technology, has been used for centuries. Tape recorders, language labs and videos have been in use since the 1960s and 1970s, and are still used in classrooms around the world. ⁴

Almost every type of language teaching has had its own technologies to support it. Language teachers who followed the Grammar-translation method, in which teachers explained grammatical rules and students performed translation, relied on the blackboard in most of their teaching. In contrast, the audio-tape was the perfect medium for the Audiolingual method, which emphasized learning through oral repetition. In the 1980s and 1990s, there has been a shift towards communicative language teaching, which emphasizes student engagement in authentic, meaningful interaction. This has led to the application of how to best integrate technology into the classroom. In spite of the fact that the use of Information and communication Technology (ICT) by language teachers is still not widespread, the use of technology in the classroom is becoming increasingly important for the presentation of authentic materials and hopefully it will become a normal part of ELT practice in the coming years. Yet teacher training programs often ignore training in the use of ICT, and teachers are often far less skilled than their own students when it comes to using current technology.

Apart from the benefits of using technology in class, there should also be mentioned the motivation that it gives to learners. With the constant advancement of technology, many ESL teachers have adopted a more fun and interesting teaching techniques to ensure exciting lessons. Motivation is the key and has been known as one of the factors that influence success in second language learning. According to Ng and Ng, motivation is known as a stimulant to achieve a specific target. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation is the two types of motivation. Intrinsic motivation can be found within the individual and related to the sense of well-being whereas extrinsic motivation comes from outside the individual.⁵ Porter (1991, as cited in Morat, Shaari, & Abidin, 2016) stated that the three important aspects related to motivation which are what energizes human behavior, what directs or channels such

⁴ Dudeney, G. and Hocky, N. (2008). *How to Teach English with Technology*. London: Longman.

⁵ Ng, C. F., & Ng, P. K. (2015). A Review of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations of ESL Learners. *International Journal of Languages, Literature and Linguistics*, 1, 98-105.

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behavior, and how this behavior is maintained or sustained. Nowadays, teachers are using technology to enrich and enhance the comprehension of the course content. Implementing multiple types of technology equipment provides ESL learners a sense of freedom, motivation, and encouragement they need for the learning process. Technology equipment such as videos provide the ability to present in both audio and visual (Canning-Wilson & Wallace, 2000) is probably the reason why it is so popular as it can increase the learners' motivation in which they perceived the teaching and learning session as interesting (Harmer, 2001).

Based on a study by Morat, Shaari, and Abidin (2016), the implementation of technology showed sustainability in the students' motivation to learn. A study conducted by Blachowicz, Bates, Berne, Bridgman, Chaney, and Perney to observe the technology used by the students, to observe the dynamics and teacher-centered choices in technology use, to look at the student learning and to learn about student and teacher perceptions and beliefs on technology. The results showed that the students were motivated and attentive when working in their task.

The use of software presentations during educational activities in schools and universities has become common due to many positive aspects. The key positive advantages of using software presentations during lessons in schools and during lectures at universities include a convenient way to present specific issues arranged in a specific chronological order, cause-and-effect sequence or other formula for dividing specific, presented issues into individual slides. The large scale of using software presentations during educational classes results from the use of a simple formula for editing individual slides and compatibility with other Ms Office system applications, as well as the possibility of pasting various types of graphic files and other materials that complement the typed text. The use of software presentations during educational activities includes the key attributes of using ICT in education.

During the presentation, the programs have a variety of advantages to the presenter and listeners. To progress through a slide show, the presenter just need to click a button, which allows the presenter to maintain eye contact with your audience and use your hands for emphasis. A software presentation often has a nice appearance and interesting graphics, which keeps the audience interested. Moreover, it can be projected on a big screen for a large auditorium or classroom. The disadvantage associated with software presentations is the need for certain requirements. A computer, projector, screen and electric power will be needed. You also need to dim the lights in the room to allow adequate visualization. The other disadvantage is the risk of technical problems. The success of the presentation depends entirely on the proper functioning of the technology.

After the presentation, the slides can be easily distributed to the necessary people for future reference. Unlike paperwork, a software presentation can be easily stored on the computer making it difficult to be lost or misplaced. The disadvantage is that the electronic file may be lost as a result of a computer virus or accidentally being deleted

Finally, I hope that software presentations will help to teachers make their lessons more effective and enjoyable for students.

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